

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarining geometrik tasavvurini rivojlantirish

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarning geometrik tasavvurini rivojlantirishga bag'ishlangan. Geometrik tasavvur, ya'ni fazoviy tafakkurning muhim komponenti sifatida, nafaqat matematika fanini o'zlashtirish, balki STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) sohalarida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun ham fundamental ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada PISA va TIMSS kabi xalqaro baholash dasturlarining natijalari tahlil qilinib, umumiy o'rta ta'lim o'quvchilarining matematik savodxonlik, xususan, geometriyaga oid ko'nikmalaridagi mavjud holat ochib berilgan. Tadqiqot Van Hiele modeli, konstruktivizm va faoliyat yondashuvi kabi nazariy asoslarga tayanib, geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishning zamonaviy metodlari вЂ“ dinamik geometriya dasturlari (masalan, GeoGebra), manipulyativ vositalar, muammoli ta'lim va STEAM-integratsiyasining samaradorligini o'rganadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, an'anaviy yodlashga asoslangan usullardan voz kechib, interaktiv, amaliy va texnologiyaga asoslangan yondashuvlarni joriy etish o'quvchilarning fazoviy tafakkurini, mantiqiy fikrlashini va muammoni yechish qobiliyatini sezilarli darajada yaxshilaydi. Maqola yakunida o'quv dasturlarini modernizatsiya qilish, o'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish va baholash tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: geometrik tasavvur, fazoviy tafakkur, matematika ta'limi, van Hiele modeli, PISA, TIMSS, STEAM, dinamik geometriya.

Abstract This article is devoted to the development of students' geometric imagination in general education schools. Geometric imagination, that is, as an important component of spatial thinking, is fundamental not only for mastering mathematics, but also for achieving success in the fields of STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). The article analyzes the results of international assessment programs such as PISA and TIMSS, revealing the current state of mathematical literacy, in particular, geometry skills of general secondary school students. The research, based on such theoretical foundations as the Van Hiele model, constructivism, and the activity approach, examines the effectiveness of modern methods for the development of geometric imagination - dynamic geometry programs (for example, GeoGebra), manipulative tools, problem-based learning, and STEAM integration. The results show that abandoning traditional memorization-based methods and implementing interactive, practical, and technology-based approaches significantly improves students' spatial thinking, logical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. At the end of the article, practical recommendations are given for modernizing curricula, improving the system of professional development and assessment of teachers.

Keywords: geometric imagination, spatial thinking, mathematics education, van Hiele

model, PISA, TIMSS, STEAM, dynamic geometry.

Kirish

XXI asr raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalar davri bo'lib, unda fan, texnologiya, muhandislik va matematika (STEAM) sohalari iqtisodiy rivojlanishning asosiy harakatlantiruvchi kuchiga aylandi [1]. Bu sohalarning barchasi uchun fundamental asos bo'lib xizmat qiladigan ko'nikmalardan biri bu \mathbb{B} fazoviy tafakkur, uning muhim tarkibiy qismi esa geometrik tasavvurdir. Shu bilan birga o'quvchilarga berilayotgan axborotlar hajmi, o'quvchilar bu axborotlarni mushohada qilish imkoniyati va undan kelajakda kerakli maqsadlarda foydalanish imkoniyatlari ancha past ekanligi kuzatilmoqda. Bu esa o'z navbatida o'qitish \mathbb{B} o'rgatishni takomillashtirishni talab etmoqda. Mavjud o'quv qo'llanmalar, darsliklar, qo'shimcha materiallar o'zining mazmuni, tuzilishi va funktsiyasi jihatidan yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlarga to'la javob bermaydi. Bundan tashqari o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlashini, ularning geometrik tasavvurlarini rivojlantiruvchi va shu tasavvur ichida mushohada qilishni ta'minlaydigan o'quv materiallari yetarli emas. Ikkinchi tomondan mustaqil fikrlay oladigan o'quvchilarni tarbiyalab voyaga yetkazish hozirgi kunning dolzarb muammolaridan biridir. Bunday shaxsni tarbiyalash jamiyatimizning rivojini ta'minlovchi, mamlakatimizda fan va texnikaning yangi texnologiyalarining rivojlanishini, insoniyatning ilm olish madaniyatining takomil topishi kabi sifatning barchasi inson tafakkuri va tasavvurisiz sodir bo'lmaydi yoki yuzaga kelmaydi. Geometrik tasavvur \mathbb{B} bu shunchaki shakllarni tanish emas, balki ob'ektlarni aqlan vizualizatsiya qilish, ularni turli burchaklardan ko'ra olish, o'zgartirish va fazodagi munosabatlarini tushunish qobiliyatidir. Bu ko'nikma arxitektura, dizayn, tibbiyot va hatto kundalik hayotda (masalan, xaritadan foydalanish yoki mebelni joylashtirish) ham muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Shu bilan birga, xalqaro tadqiqotlar ko'plab mamlakatlarda, jumladan, O'zbekistonda ham o'quvchilarning matematik savodxonligi, ayniqsa, amaliy geometriya va fazoviy masalalarni yechish bo'yicha ko'nikmalari yetarli darajada emasligini ko'rsatmoqda. Iqtisodiy hamkorlik va taraqqiyot tashkiloti (OECD) tomonidan o'tkazilgan PISA-2022 tadqiqotida O'zbekiston ilk bor ishtirok etdi va 15 yoshli o'quvchilarning matematika bo'yicha o'rtacha bali 364 ni tashkil etdi, bu OECD mamlakatlari o'rtacha ko'rsatkichidan pastdir. O'quvchilarning atigi 19 foizi matematikadan minimal (2-daraja) malaka darajasiga erishgan, OECD bo'yicha bu ko'rsatkich 69 foizni tashkil etadi. Bu natijalar ta'lim tizimida, xususan, abstrakt va mantiqiy fikrlashni talab qiluvchi geometriya o'qitish metodikasini qayta ko'rib chiqish zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

An'anaviy ta'limda geometriya ko'pincha formulalar va teoremlarni yodlashga asoslangan holda o'qitiladi, bu esa o'quvchilarda geometriya faniga nisbatan qiziqishning so'nishiga va tasavvur qilish qobiliyatining sust rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Zero, zamonaviy didaktika o'qitish jarayonini o'quvchining faol ishtirokiga, amaliy mashg'ulotlarga va texnologiyalardan unumli foydalanishga qurishni talab etadi [2]. Van Hiele tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan geometrik tafakkur darajalari nazariyasi o'quvchilarning geometriyani qanday o'zlashtirishini bosqichma-bosqich tushuntirib, har bir daraja uchun mos o'qitish strategiyalarini taklif qiladi [3].

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi \mathbb{B} O'zbekiston umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarning geometrik tasavvurini rivojlantirishning dolzarb muammolarini tahlil qilish, xalqaro ilg'or tajribalar va nazariy yondashuvlar asosida samarali metodik yechimlarni taklif etishdan iborat. Maqolada geometrik tasavvurning mohiyati, uni

shakllantiruvchi komponentlar, zamonaviy o'qitish metodlari va baholash usullari atroficha ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'qituvchilar, metodistlar va ta'lim siyosatchilari uchun amaliy qo'llanma bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Metodlar

Ushbu tadqiqot deduktiv-analitik yondashuvga asoslangan bo'lib, unda umumiy o'rta ta'limda geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishga oid mavjud adabiyotlarni tizimli tahlil qilish (systematic literature review) metodi qo'llanilgan. Tadqiqot doirasida nazariy va amaliy manbalar tanlab olinib, ulardagi asosiy g'oyalar, metodlar va natijalar umumlashtirildi va O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi kontekstida tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi bir necha bosqichdan iborat bo'ldi.

Birinchi bosqichda O'quvchilar bilimini faollashtirish va qayta ishlash, ma'lumotlar manbalarini aniqlash va yig'ish ishlari olib borildi. Buning uchun quyidagi turdagi hujjatlar o'rganildi: 1) Xalqaro baholash dasturlari hisobotlari, xususan, Iqtisodiy hamkorlik va taraqqiyot tashkilotining (OECD) PISA-2022 va Ta'limdagi yutuqlarni baholash xalqaro assotsiatsiyasining (IEA) TIMSS-2019 va TIMSS-2023 [4, 5] natijalari; 2) Nufuzli ilmiy jurnallarda (masalan, Springer, ScienceDirect, Frontiers, PMC NCBI) chop etilgan fazoviy tafakkur, geometrik fikrlash va matematika ta'limi metodikasiga oid 2020-2025-yillardagi maqolalar [3, 6]; 3) UNESCO va Jahon Banki kabi xalqaro tashkilotlarning ta'lim sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan tahliliy hisobotlari va tavsiyalari [7]; 4) O'zbekiston Respublikasining ta'lim sohasidagi me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlari, jumladan, Davlat ta'lim standartlari, milliy o'quv dasturlari va matematika fanini o'qitishga oid metodik qo'llanmalar [8, 9].

Ikkinchi bosqichda to'plangan yangi ko'nikma va malakani rivojlantirish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish uchun nazariy asoslar tanlandi. Asosiy nazariy model sifatida van Hiele geometrik tafakkur darajalari (vizualizatsiya, tahlil, tartiblash, deduksiya, qat'iylik) modeli olindi [3, 10]. Ushbu model o'quvchilarning geometrik tushunchalarni o'zlashtirish jarayonini tushunish va o'qitish strategiyalarini har bir darajaga moslashtirish uchun qulay asos yaratadi. Shuningdek, tahlilda konstruktivizm (o'quvchi bilimni o'zi faol yaratadi) va faoliyat yondashuvi (bilim amaliy faoliyat orqali egallanadi) tamoyillaridan foydalanildi [2].

Uchinchi bosqichda yangi ko'nikma va malakaning amaliyotga tatbiq etish, tahlil natijalari sintez qilindi. Turli manbalardan olingan ma'lumotlar, statistik ko'rsatkichlar va metodik yondashuvlar o'zaro taqqoslanib, geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishning samarali modelini yaratishga xizmat qiluvchi asosiy komponentlar ajratib olindi. Jumladan, rivojlantirish metodlari (dinamik geometriya, manipulyativlar, STEAM), baholash vositalari (rubrikalar, portfoliolar) va amaliyotdagi cheklovlar (resurs, o'qituvchi malakasi) tizimlashtirildi. Tadqiqotning ishonchliligi va xolisligini ta'minlash maqsadida faqat nufuzli va tasdiqlangan manbalarga tayanildi, statistik ma'lumotlar manbasi aniq ko'rsatildi.

Natijalar

Tahlil natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quvchilarning geometrik tasavvurini rivojlantirish ko'p qirrali jarayon bo'lib, u ham nazariy, ham amaliy jihatdan chuqur yondashuvni talab etadi. Natijalar bir necha asosiy yo'nalishlarda umumlashtirildi: xalqaro va milliy baholashlar konteksti, geometrik tasavvurning tarkibiy tuzilmasi va uni rivojlantirishning zamonaviy metodlari.

Xalqaro baholash dasturlari o'quvchilarning amaliy ko'nikmalarini, jumladan, geometrik materialni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda qo'llay olish qobiliyatini o'lchaydi. PISA-2022 natijalariga ko'ra, O'zbekistonlik o'quvchilarning matematik savodxonlik bo'yicha ko'rsatkichlari (364 ball) OECD o'rtacha ko'rsatkichidan (472 ball) sezilarli darajada past. Topshiriqlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quvchilar ko'proq standart algoritmlarni bajarishga qiynalmasa-da, nostandart, vizualizatsiya va modellashtirishni talab etuvchi masalalarda jiddiy qiyinchiliklarga duch keladi. Masalan, PISA topshiriqlaridan biri bo'lgan "Ferma tomi"(Farmhouse Roof) masalasida o'quvchidan piramida shaklidagi tomning matematik modelini tahlil qilib, uning elementlarini hisoblash talab etiladi, bu esa kuchli fazoviy tasavvurni nazarda tutadi [11].

IEA tomonidan o'tkazilgan TIMSS-2023 tadqiqoti ham shunga o'xshash manzarani ko'rsatadi. 4-sinf o'quvchilarining matematika bo'yicha natijasi 443 ball (58 davlat orasida 50-o'rin), 8-sinf o'quvchilariniki esa 421 ball (44 davlat orasida 32-o'rin) bo'lgan [5]. TIMSS baholash mezonlarida "Geometriya va o'lchashlar"(Geometry and Measurement) alohida blok sifatida ajratilgan bo'lib, 8-sinf uchun bu yo'nalish umumiy ballning 20%ini tashkil etadi [4]. Bu natijalar milliy o'quv dasturlari va o'qitish amaliyotida geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishga yetarlicha e'tibor qaratilmayotganidan dalolat beradi.

Geometrik tasavvurni shakllantirishning tarkibiy qismlari va metodlari

Ilmiy adabiyotlar tahlili geometrik tasavvurni bir nechta o'zaro bog'liq komponentlarga ajratish mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Bular: fazoviy vizualizatsiya, mental aylantirish, fazoviy munosabatlarni anglash va shakl-zaminni ajratish kabi qobiliyatlardir [8, 11]. Ushbu komponentlarning har birini tizimli rivojlantirish uchun maxsus metodik yondashuvlar talab etiladi. Quyidagi jadvalda geometrik tasavvurning asosiy komponentlari, ularni rivojlantirish metodlari va baholash mezonlari umumlashtirilgan.

1-jadval. Geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishning komponentlari, metodlari va baholash mezonlari

№,–	Komponent	Indikator	Rivojlantirish metodlari	Baholash vositalari
1	Fazoviy vizualizatsiya	2 va 3 o'lchovli fazoda shakllarni tasavvur qilish; yoyilma va yig'ma holatni anglash.	GeoGebra, Desmos; kompyuter modellar; qog'ozdan shakl yasash.	Yoyilmadan shaklni aniqlash testlari; turli ko'rinishlarini chizish.
2	Mental aylantirish	Ob'ektni xayolan o'qlar atrofida aylantirib yangi holatini aniqlash.	Kubiklar, konstruktorlar; Rubik kubi; 3D o'yinlar.	Aylantirilgan shakllarni taqqoslash testlari (Vandenberg va Kuse).
3	Shakl-tuzilma tahlili	Murakkab shaklni sodda geometrik qismlarga ajratish.	Konstruksiya masalalari; shakl tahlili; STEAM loyihalari.	Yuza va perimetrni topish; vektorliqchasini topishni topshiriqlari.
4	Mantiqiy dalillash	Geometrik mulohazalarni mantiqiy zanjir asosida tuzish.	Van Hiele (3 va 4 bosqich); vektorliqchasini mulohazalari.	Ochiq masalalar; isbotdagi xatoni topish.

Таблица 1: Fazoviy tafakkurni rivojlantirish komponentlari

Rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, an'anaviy "doska-bo'r" formatidan voz kechib, o'quv jarayoniga interaktiv texnologiyalar va amaliy faoliyatni integratsiya qilish geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishda yuqori samara beradi. Masalan, Tunisda 1-sinf o'quvchilari

bilan o'tkazilgan tajribada "Xazina o'yini"(Treasure Game) deb nomlangan harakatli o'yin an'anaviy darslarga qaraganda geometrik fikrlash darajasini va o'quvchilarning kayfiyatini sezilarli darajada oshirgan [12]. Bu o'yin davomida bolalar jamoa bo'lib geometrik shakllarni o'z tanalari yordamida "chizishgan bu esa ularning fazoni his qilishini va jismoniy tajriba orqali tushunchalarni o'zlashtirishini ta'minlagan.

Dinamik geometriya dasturlari (DGS), xususan, GeoGebra, o'qitish jarayonida inqilobiy o'zgarish yasadi. Ular o'quvchilarga geometrik ob'ektlarni shunchaki chizish emas, balki ularni "jonli" tarzda o'zgartirish, nuqtalarni siljitish orqali xossalar qanday o'zgarishini kuzatish imkonini beradi. Bu jarayon o'quvchilarda gipotezalar yaratish va ularni shu zahotiy oq tekshirib ko'rish malakasini shakllantiradi, bu esa van Hiele modelining yuqori bosqichlariga o'tishni tezlashtiradi [132]. Tadqiqotlar DGSdan foydalanish o'quvchilarning geometriyadan o'zlashtirishini va fazoviy tafakkurini yaxshilashini tasdiqlaydi [4].

STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) yondashuvi fanlarni alohida emas, balki o'zaro integratsiyada, real hayotiy loyihalar orqali o'rganishni taklif etadi [1]. Geometriya STEAM loyihalari uchun tabiiy platforma hisoblanadi. Masalan, o'quvchilar arxitektura elementlarini o'rganib, geometrik printsiplar asosida bino yoki ko'prik modelini yaratishlari, bunda mustahkamlikni hisoblash uchun matematikadan, dizayn uchun san'atdan va materiallarni tanlash uchun texnologiyadan foydalanishlari mumkin. Bu jarayon geometriyani zerikarli fandan amaliy va ijodiy faoliyatga aylantiradi.

Muhokama

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekiston umumta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarning geometrik tasavvurini rivojlantirish masalasi tizimli va kompleks yondashuvni talab qiladi. PISA va TIMSS kabi xalqaro baholashlardagi past natijalar shunchaki bilimlar yetishmasligini emas, balki o'quvchilarning fikrlash ko'nikmalari, xususan, bilimlarni nostandart vaziyatlarda qo'llash va fazoviy mulohaza yuritish qobiliyati yetarli shakllanmaganini ko'rsatadi [5]. Bu muammoning ildizi an'anaviy o'qitish metodlarida, ya'ni tayyor bilimlarni uzatish va yodlashga asoslangan yondashuvda yotadi.

Geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirish uchun taklif etilayotgan metodik model (2-rasm) o'quv jarayonini o'quvchining individual xususiyatlari va tayyorgarlik darajasidan kelib chiqqan holda, aniq didaktik tamoyillar asosida qurishni nazarda tutadi. Bu modelda asosiy urg'u faoliyatga, vizualizatsiyaga va amaliyotga qaratilgan. Van Hiele nazariyasi ko'rsatganidek, o'quvchi geometrik tafakkurning bir darajasidan keyingisiga o'tishi uchun maxsus tashkil etilgan, yo'naltirilgan faoliyat bosqichlaridan o'tishi kerak [3, 10]. Dinamik geometriya dasturlari, manipulyativlar va STEAM loyihalari aynan shunday faoliyatni tashkil etish uchun samarali vositalardir.

Biroq, bu zamonaviy metodlarni amaliyotga joriy etish bir qator cheklovlar va qiyinchiliklar bilan bog'liq. Birinchidan, bu o'qituvchilardan yuqori darajadagi kasbiy mahorat va yangi texnologiyalarni egallashni talab qiladi. Ko'plab o'qituvchilarning o'zlari an'anaviy tizimda ta'lim olgan va ularning geometrik tafakkur darajasi van Hiele shkalasi bo'yicha yuqori bo'lmasligi mumkin [14]. Shu sababli, o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish kurslarini tubdan qayta ko'rib chiqish, ularni amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan, loyihaga asoslangan va zamonaviy vositalardan foydalanishga o'rgatadigan formatda tashkil etish lozim [9, 15].

2-rasm. O'quvchilarda geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishning metodik modeli. Model o'qitish jarayonini tizimli loyihalashga yordam beradi.

Ikkinchidan, maktablarning moddiy-texnik bazasi ham muhim omil. Har bir sinfni kompyuterlar, interaktiv doskalar va dinamik dasturlar bilan ta'minlash, shuningdek, amaliy mashg'ulotlar uchun yetarli miqdorda manipulyativ vositalar (geometrik jismlar to'plamlari, konstruktorlar) bilan jihozlash zarur. Uchinchidan, mavjud o'quv dasturlari va darsliklar ko'pincha nazariy materialga haddan tashqari yuklangan bo'lib, amaliy va ijodiy topshiriqlar uchun yetarli vaqt va o'rin qoldirmaydi [16]. Dasturlarni qayta ko'rib chiqishda geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirishga alohida urg'u berish, mavzularni spiral prinsipida (boshlang'ich sinflardan boshlab bosqichma-bosqich murakkablashtirib borish) o'qitish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, O'zbekiston maktablarida geometriya o'qitishni isloh qilish va "bu shunchaki darsliklarni yangilash emas, balki butun bir pedagogik falsafani o'zgartirish demakdir. Bu o'zgarish o'quvchini passiv tinglovchidan faol tadqiqotchiga, o'qituvchini esa ma'lumot uzatuvchidan o'quv jarayonining muhandisi va yo'naltiruvchisiga aylantirishni talab qiladi [2]. Geometrik tasavvurni rivojlantirish orqali biz nafaqat matematikani yaxshi o'zlashtiradigan, balki tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlaydigan, murakkab muammolarga nostandart yechim topa oladigan avlodni tarbiyalashga erishamiz. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, mamlakatning innovatsion salohiyatini yuksaltirish uchun mustahkam poydevor bo'ladi.

Amaliy tavsiyalar

Yuqoridagi tahlillar asosida maktablar va o'qituvchilar uchun quyidagi bosqichma-bosqich tavsiyalarni berish mumkin:

1. **Diagnostika va rejalashtirish:** O'quv yili boshida o'quvchilarning geometrik tafakkur darajasini van Hiele modeliga asoslangan sodda testlar yordamida aniqlash. Natijalarga ko'ra sinfni shartli guruhlarga ajratib, har bir guruh uchun tabaqalashtirilgan topshiriqlar rejasini tuzish.

2. **Metodlarni integratsiya qilish:** Har bir darsda nazariya va amaliyotni uyg'unlashtirish. An'anaviy masala yechish bilan birga, kamida 10-15 daqiqa vaqtni amaliy faoliyatga (masalan, GeoGebra'da yasash, model yasash, guruhda loyiha ishlash) ajratish.

3. **Texnologiyalardan foydalanish:** GeoGebra, Desmos kabi bepul va qulay dasturlardan darsda va uy vazifalarida keng foydalanish. O'qituvchilar o'zlari kichik interaktiv dars ishlanmalarini yaratib, o'quvchilar bilan bo'lishishlari mumkin.

4. **Baholashni o'zgartirish:** Yakuniy nazorat ishlaridan tashqari, formativ baholash usullarini (kuzatish, savol-javob, kichik loyihalar) faol qo'llash. O'quvchilarning geometriyaga oid ijodiy ishlaridan (chizmalar, modellar, taqdimotlar) iborat portfolioni yuritish va uni baholash.

5. **Kasbiy rivojlanish:** O'qituvchilar o'zaro tajriba almashish uchun "kasbiy o'rganish jamoalari"(professional learning communities) tashkil etishlari, zamonaviy metodikalar bo'yicha onlayn kurslar va seminarlarda muntazam ishtirok etib borishlari lozim.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Abidjanovna, M. G. (2024). Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish zaruriyati. Cyberleninka.

2. Tchoshanov, M. (2013). Engineering of Learning: Conceptualizing e-Didactics. UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education.

3. Chikha, A. B., Hawani, A., Eken, F., et al. (2024). The impact of the treasure game on geometric thinking and post-learning mood in first-grade children. *Medicine*, 103(50), e40695. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000040695>

4. IEA. (2024). TIMSS 2023 International Results in Mathematics and Science. Boston College. <https://timss2023.org/results/>

5. Xolmirzayev, F. G. (2025). TIMSS 2023 tadqiqotida O'zbekiston natijasi haqida. *Inter education & global study*, 2.

6. Almubarak, M. (2025). Evolving Three Decades of Geometry Learning Strategies: A Combination of Bibliometric Analysis and Systematic Literature Review. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 21(5), em2589.

7. UNESCO. (2021). Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education. UNESCO Publishing.

8. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 1999-yil 16-avgustdagi Umumiy o'rta ta'limning davlat ta'lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to'g'risida 390-sonli qarori. <https://lex.uz/mact/-316337>

9. Parmonov, H.F. (2024). Matematika o'qitish metodikasi (O'quv-uslubiy majmua). O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti.

10. Vojkuvkova, I. (2012). The van Hiele model of geometric thinking. *WDS'12 Proceedings of Contributed Papers*, 72-75.

11. OECD. (2023). Released Items from the PISA 2022 Computer-Based Mathematics Assessment. OECD Publishing.

12. Xalimov, M. K. (2023). Modulli-kompetentli yondashuv asosida talabalarning

fazoviy tasavvurini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish. Cyberleninka.

13. Sobirova, M. (2021). Novyy kreativnyy podkhod k obucheniyu geometrii v sredney shkole Uzbekistana. *Jamiyat va innovatsiyalar*, 1, 216-221.

14. Robichaux-Davis, R. R., & Guarino, A. J. (2016). Assessing elementary pre-service teachers' knowledge for teaching geometry. *International Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Invention*, 4(1), 12-20.

15. Jolanov, D. Q. (2021). Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida geometrik shakllarni va materialni o'rgatish jarayonida ko'rgazma hamda didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish. Cyberleninka.

16. O'rinboyeva, L. (2021). Matematika 1-sinf (Darslik). Respublika ta'lim markazi.

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